

Studies on Thiazolidinones as Potential Antitubercular Compounds

M. P. DAVE, J. M. PATEL, N. A. LANGALIA and K. A. THAKER*

University Department of Chemistry, Bhavnagar University, Bhavnagar-364 002

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2-Aryl-3-(4-amino-3,5-dibromobenzamido)-5-substituted-4-thiazolidinones (2 and 3) have been prepared by condensation of mercaptoalkanoic acids with azomethines (1). The compounds show antitubercular activity, when tested against $H_{87}R_v$ strain.

THIAZOLIDINONE derivatives exhibit a variety of pharmacological activities^{1,2}. Thiazolidinones have been found to possess antitubercular activity³. The nucleus is also active as hypnotic and anaesthetic⁴. The presence of N—C—S linkage has been postulated to account for the antifungal activity of 4-thiazolidinones⁵.

Acid hydrazides and their condensation products have gained prominence as tuberculostatic⁶, antifungal antileprotic⁷ and antihelminthic⁸ agents. Buu-Hoi *et al.*⁹ have synthesised a large number of hydrazides and their condensation products with various aldehydes in view of the possibility of their being less toxic than parent hydrazides due to

blocking of free NH_2 group. A literature review has revealed that condensation of aromatic aldehyde with acid hydrazide of 4-amino-3,5-dibromobenzoic acid has not been studied so far.

The present communication deals with the synthesis and pharmacological studies of some 4-thiazolidinones¹⁰ of the type 2 and 3, the Schiff¹¹ bases of 4-amino-3,5-dibromobenzoic acid hydrazide have been prepared with different aromatic aldehydes and condensed with thioglycolic acid and thiomallic acid. When tested, these compounds (2 and 3) show antitubercular activity against $H_{87}R_v$ strain in Lowenstein-Jensen's egg medium (4 ml). Infrared spectra of the title compounds have been taken on a Spectromom 2000 spectrophotometer. The strong bands at 1750 and 1760 cm^{-1} were characteristic carbonyl stretching frequency for thiazolidinone ring system. All the reaction sequences have been reported in Scheme 1

where, R = different aromatic moiety and $R' = CH_2COOH$ or H.

Scheme 1

Experimental

Melting points of the compounds were determined in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. The structure of the compounds have been established on the bases of their elemental analysis and infrared spectrum.

4-Amino-3,5-dibromo benzoic acid hydrazide : It was prepared by known method¹².

1-(4-Amino-3,5-dibromobenzoyl)-2-benzylidene hydrazine : To the solution of aldehyde (benzaldehyde) (0.01 M) in ethanol (50 ml; 95%) was added 4-amino-3,5-dibromo benzoic acid hydrazide (0.01 M) in ethanol (50 ml; 95%); the contents heated to reflux for 2 h, cooled and worked out to get the corresponding Schiff's base.

2-Phenyl-3-(4-amino-3,5-dibromo benzamido)-4-thiazolidinone : 1-(4-Amino-3,5-dibromobenzoyl)-2-benzylidene hydrazine (0.01 M), benzene (100 ml) and thioglycolic acid (0.012 M) were refluxed (25 h) using Dean and Stark separator. The solvent was

then removed, residue treated with NaHCO_3 solution and filtered when thiazolidinone crystallised from ethanol.

2-(2-Chloro phenyl)-3-(4-amino-3,5-dibromobenzamido)-5-carboxymethyl-4-thiazolidinone : 1-(4-Amino-3,5-dibromobenzoyl)-2-(2-chloro)benzylidene hydrazine (0.01 M) and thiomallic acid (0.01 M) were condensed in presence of anhydrous zinc chloride (0.5 g) at 160° for 2 h on oil-bath and the temperature raised to 180° for 30 min. The product so obtained was dissolved in sodium bicarbonate solution (4 N) and filtered; the filtrate reprecipitated

with dilute hydrochloric acid and crystallised from ethanol (95%).

The physical data of 1 and 2 are presented in Tables 1 and 2.

Biological screening : The *in vitro* antimycobacterial activity of the compounds were studied at 0, 5 and $30 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ (solvent: DMF) against $H_{37}R_v$ strain of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* using Lowenstein-Jensen egg medium. The retardation of growth rate was studied upto 6 weeks at 37° . The procedure was duplicated using only solvent for control purpose.

TABLE 1—DATA OF COMPOUNDS 1

Sl. no.	R	M.p. °C	Yield %	N%: Found/(Calcd.)
1.	C_6H_5	245	60	10.70 (10.58)
2.	2-Cl- C_6H_4	285	62	9.93 (9.73)
3.	3-Cl- C_6H_4	220	66	9.84 (9.73)
4.	3- NO_2 - C_6H_4	260	58	12.79 (12.67)
5.	4- NO_2 - C_6H_4	320	55	12.78 (12.67)
6.	2- OCH_3 - C_6H_4	240	67	9.94 (9.81)
7.	2-OH- C_6H_4	280	64	10.30 (10.17)
8.	4-OH- C_6H_4	284	57	10.05 (10.17)
9.	3,4- CH_2O_2 - C_6H_3	270	53	9.40 (9.52)
10.	3- OCH_3 -4-OH- C_6H_3	244	65	9.61 (9.48)
11.	3,4-di- OCH_3 - C_6H_3	248	59	9.31 (9.19)
12.	3,5-di-Br-2-OH- C_6H_3	169	67	7.48 (7.36)

From the experimental data it has been concluded that the thiazolidinones (2) are tuberculostatic at $30 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$. Further, substitution in benzene ring or presence of carboxymethyl group at position-5 of the thiazolidine ring have no significant effect on tuberculostatic activity. In contrast to thiazolidinones (2), the corresponding hydrazones (1) do not inhibit the growth of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* ($H_{37}R_v$ strain) reflecting the key role of thiazolidinone structure for tuberculostatic activity.

Results and Discussion

The *in vitro* antimycobacterial screening results show that all the compounds are inactive at 0 and $5 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ and active at $30 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$. Therefore, only conclusion that can be drawn from these results is that the compounds 2 and 3 are active at higher concentration rather than at lower concentration.

TABLE 2—DATA OF COMPOUNDS 2 and 3

Sl. no.	R	R'	M.p. °C	Yield %	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)	
					N	S
1.	- C_6H_5	H	161	71	9.04 (8.92)	6.90 (6.79)
2.	3- NO_2 - C_6H_4	H	270	68	10.96 (10.85)	6.31 (6.20)
3.	4- NO_2 - C_6H_4	H	203	64	10.96 (10.85)	6.35 (6.20)
4.	2- OCH_3 - C_6H_4	H	221	75	8.47 (8.37)	6.25 (6.37)
5.	2-OH- C_6H_4	H	228	77	8.77 (8.62)	6.71 (6.57)
6.	3,4-di- OCH_3 - C_6H_3	H	224	72	8.05 (7.91)	6.14 (6.03)
7.	2-Cl- C_6H_4	CH_2COOH	176	52	7.56 (7.45)	5.54 (5.67)
8.	3-Cl- C_6H_4	CH_2COOH	147	74	7.60 (7.45)	5.78 (5.67)
9.	3,5-di-Br-2-OH- C_6H_3	CH_2COOH	135	70	5.84 (5.97)	4.65 (4.95)
10.	4-OH- C_6H_4	CH_2COOH	216	69	7.85 (7.71)	6.03 (5.87)
11.	3,4- CH_2O_2 - C_6H_3	CH_2COOH	225	65	7.62 (7.49)	5.57 (5.70)
12.	3- OCH_3 -4-OH- C_6H_3	CH_2COOH	270	72	7.19 (7.30)	5.67 (5.56)

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